

Continuing education for teachers in Educational Robotics: Introduction to Programming with Arduino and Micro:bit

Leonardo Mesquita¹, Galeno José de Sena¹, Samuel Euzédice de Lucena¹, Marco Aurélio Alvarenga Monteiro¹, Jânio Itiro Akamatsu¹

¹ São Paulo State University - UNESP, Faculty of Engineering and Sciences, Guaratinguetá, Brazil

Email: leonardo.mesquita@unesp.br, galeno.sena@unesp.br, samuel.lucena@unesp.br, marco.monteiro@unesp.br, janio.akamatsu@unesp.br

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880125>

ABSTRACT

This article aims to describe the actions of a project developed at UNESP, Guaratinguetá Campus, Brazil, aimed at training teachers for the public school system in the region of the Guaratinguetá Education Board (DE). The project was developed in partnership with the Guaratinguetá Education Board and included the offering of an Educational Robotics course based on the Arduino and Micro:bit platforms. The emphasis on these two platforms was justified by considering the curricular guidelines for public schools in the state of São Paulo, as well as the availability of platform kits in these schools. An essential aspect of using technologies in schools is to prepare teachers for their use in the classroom. Therefore, the course aimed to complement the level of theoretical and practical knowledge in the area of Robotics of basic education teachers, demonstrating the potential of using robotics for teaching multiple content areas. The actions were conducted according to the guidelines of a Project-Based Learning (PBL) model, aiming to investigate, among other aspects, strategies for the use of PBL in a traditional teaching context. In addition, the actions included the presentation and discussion of topics related to the development of Computational Thinking. The article briefly presents the objectives of the course offered, aspects of its development, as well as the results of its evaluation. The results obtained demonstrate the suitability of this approach for preparing teachers to develop teaching projects with topics of Educational Robotics with their students in their schools.

Keywords: Teacher training; Educational Robotics; Computational Thinking; Arduino; micro:bit.

1 Introduction

This article aims to describe the actions of a project developed at UNESP, Guaratinguetá Campus, Brazil, aimed at training teachers for the public school system in the region of the Guaratinguetá Education Directorate (DE). The project began in 2022 and had the support of the Legislative Assembly of the State of São Paulo, via State Parliamentary Amendment No. 2022.088.38181, for the purpose of funding and investing in the training of teachers for the public school system of the State of São Paulo.

One of the motivations for developing the project is the fact that Basic Education schools have had difficulty changing their pedagogical practices to the new proposal of teaching by skills and competencies, recommended by the new National Common Curricular Base - BNCC (Gerhard & Rocha, 2012). An essential aspect of using technology in schools is preparing teachers for its use. In other words, it is necessary to present, train and provide instructions on when and how to use a given resource in the classroom. The better prepared a teacher is to use a new technological resource, such as Educational Robotics, for example, the more likely they are to be successful in using this tool in the classroom. In this context, it is necessary to redefine certain pedagogical practices to prepare students to face real problems, instead of artificial ones, which are often applied in a decontextualized way in the classroom, giving students a greater role in the teaching and learning process.

The article briefly presents the objectives of the robotics training course offered, as well as the results of its evaluation. The article is organized as follows. In this section, a general presentation of the project is made. Section 2 presents the theoretical basis of the project. The methodology used is presented in section 3. Section 4 describes the development of the project, presenting the objectives of the course offered. Results of the

evaluations of the course by the participants are presented in section 5. Section 6 presents some conclusions and discussions arising from the development of the project.

2 Theoretical basis and related works

The project sought to base its actions in a manner consistent with the BNCC (BRAZIL, 2018), a document from the Federal Government (Ministry of Education) that contains the curricular guidelines that must be followed by basic education schools. The BNCC is based on two premises: the integral formation of the human being and the construction of a more just, democratic and inclusive society.

The BNCC establishes as a goal, for the entire Basic Education path, the development of ten (10) general competencies to be worked on with all students. The emphasis on the use of digital information and communication technologies - ICT, in the different stages of Basic Education, is included in these competencies. For example, competency 5 defends the importance of:

"Understand, use and create digital information and communication technologies in a critical, meaningful, reflective and ethical way in various social practices (including school practices) to communicate, access and disseminate information, produce knowledge, solve problems and exercise protagonism and authorship in personal and collective life." (BRASIL, 2018, p. 9)

It can therefore be seen that the inclusion of Robotics in the educational context is consistent with this competence. Regarding this inclusion, one can initially mention the development of the LOGO language by Seymour Papert and other researchers, which allowed children to control a robotic turtle through computer commands (Massa et al., 2022). The language was developed in the 1960s, when the foundations of computing were still being established. The programming of the robot by children, which was carried out through a computer, made it possible, for example, to draw various geometric figures. Papert was convinced that the machine would be able to change the way children learn, considering that this learning process would occur through the creation, reflection and refinement of ideas. Papert's vision remains relevant to this day, encouraging several schools to adopt methodologies and disciplines that work on this learning process, as is the case of Robotics actions used as instruments to support learning in various disciplines.

In the 1980s, Papert and his research group at MIT began a partnership with the LEGO company, which resulted in the LEGO/Logo system in 1986, which allowed children to build various mechanical artifacts that were connected to an interface and whose movements could be programmed using the Logo language. This system was the first widely available robotics construction kit (Martin et al., 2000).

The inclusion of Educational Robotics in schools must include teacher training programs because, as Reis et al. (2014) point out, it is not enough for schools to have materials such as robotics kits available if there are no trained personnel to use them appropriately in the classroom. The authors also recognize the multidisciplinary nature of Educational Robotics, emphasizing that it is not widely explored by schools, especially public schools, partly due to the costs involved in purchasing the kits, but also due to the lack of trained personnel to use them. In this context, the authors highlight the relevance of establishing partnerships between Universities and schools, as "an important means of introducing educational robotics into primary and secondary education" (Reis et al., 2014, p. 56).

The project developed by Vargas e Silva et al. (2018) also presents a teacher training program aimed at basic education teachers, carried out in 10 3-hour meetings, using the Criatecno CT100® Educational Robotics kit, based on the Arduino platform. The project is part of a university extension program, with training activities being carried out on the university campus (Feevale). The programming of the kit's control board was carried out using the Ardublock language, which is based on predefined blocks. In addition to the training program, the project also included workshops using the LEGO®MINDSTORM® NXT kit, aimed at students in the final years of elementary school and high school students. The workshops could take place both at the university and in schools, with the necessary kits being made available by Feevale.

Da Fonseca Silva et al. (2018) present the results of a survey conducted with teachers at a private Early Childhood Education school that included Educational Robotics in its curriculum. Robotics classes were offered

to students aged 3 to 6 years old, who carried out the activities in groups of up to 4 participants, assembling them using LEGO® kits. In the conclusions of the study, the authors suggest the need for further discussions on the use of Robotics in schools, and highlight, in this context, the need for better teacher training to use this resource in the classroom, thus contributing to more meaningful learning on the part of students.

Pinto et al. (2012) describe the implementation of a teacher training course in Educational Robotics, which is structured in two axes, namely: the technological axis and the pedagogical axis. The technological axis comprises two dimensions, hardware and software, being: (i) hardware – computer, Arduino and electronic components; and (ii) software – environment and application development language for Arduino. The pedagogical axis is structured according to a model designated as the Hierarchical Model of Interactivity in three layers - MHI-3C, which corresponds to the following interaction modalities: researcher-teacher (layer 1), teacher-teacher (layer 2) and teacher-student (layer 3). The proposals for teaching activities and their application in the classroom context occurred in layers 2 and 3. The authors argue, in relation to this form of organization, that "in the context of educational robotics, the role of the teacher is of great importance, acting both in the planning and in the execution of his teaching activity with the resources of robotics" (Pinto et al., 2012, p. 161).

The work of Souza et al. (2016) aimed to analyze the effects of introducing Computational Thinking (CT) in the training of robotics teachers at SESI-PB, Brazil. The project was proposed considering the difficulties presented by teachers and students, mainly in the robot programming stage. Thus, the first phase of the project consisted of offering an introductory course on CT for teachers and students of high school at SESI-PB. The results obtained highlight the need, in the context of Educational Robotics, for teaching CT for teacher and student training. The authors also point out that "there is evidence that CT positively influences student performance" (Souza et al., 2016, p. 1266).

3 Methods and procedures

The methodological approach of the research was based, mainly in its initial phase, on action research (Tripp, 2005), since the actions to be developed were structured jointly with the Curriculum Specialist Teachers - PEC, from the areas of Mathematics and Technology, from DE Guaratinguetá, establishing a link between the university team and the teachers of the schools that would participate in the course. Furthermore, according to Tripp (2005), one of the characteristics of action research is that it is participatory, thus differentiating itself from routine practice (individual) and scientific research (team/collegiate), and also being "collaborative in its way of working" (Tripp, 2005, p. 448). Under this approach, the teachers of the courses should participate in the training activities, propose and carry out teaching projects using Educational Robotics with the students of their schools, supervised by the University team.

The course activities were developed according to the guidelines of a PBL Project-Based Learning model, aiming to investigate, among other aspects, strategies for the use of PBL in a traditional teaching context, and the role of active learning – students participating in the development of projects involving Educational Robotics in their schools – in improving the learning of concepts related to the themes Rational Use of Energy and Energy Efficiency.

The PBL model used was that of the BIE Institute – Buck Institute for Education (www.bie.org) (Markham et al., 2008), which presents PBL as an appropriate model to deal with the educational reality of the 21st century, emphasizing the contextual and interdisciplinary nature of learning. Duch et al. (2006) emphasize that the content to be addressed in a PBL application should aim to develop "higher-level" thinking skills in students, aiming to acquire the cognitive levels established by Bloom's taxonomy: knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation (sense of judgment) (Bloom, 1956, as cited in Duch et al., 2006). This taxonomy was revised in 2001, giving rise to Bloom's revised Taxonomy, in which the cognitive domain categories are: remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, synthesizing and creating (Ferraz & Belhot, 2010), which should be emphasized in an application of PBL in the current context.

The BIE Institute proposes a PBL model focused on standards (Markham et al., 2008), with the structuring of a project based on the principles described briefly below: (I) Begin with the end in mind: defining, among other aspects, the content standards, key skills and habits of mind that will constitute the expected results of the project; (II) Formulate the Guiding Question: proposing a relevant and meaningful question that will get students involved in the project, requiring them to take an active stance and dedication to seek their own answers and their own knowledge (Poza, 1998); (III) Plan the evaluation: specify the expected products and artifacts of the project and how they will be evaluated, noting that the evaluation, in a PBL application, is usually based on performance, as it involves a problem-solving activity. (IV) Map the project: includes, among other aspects, the organization of the tasks and activities to be developed, the selection of the necessary resources and the preparation of a visual script (which can be a storyboard or a schedule, among others); (V) Manage the process: describe tools and strategies to assist in managing the development of the project.

4 Justification and development

Preparing teachers to use new technologies in schools, as already mentioned, is an essential aspect, that is, it is necessary to present, train and provide recommendations on when and how to use a given resource in the classroom. After all, the indiscriminate and, in some cases, mechanical use of new technologies may not promote desirable qualitative and quantitative changes in the teaching and learning process. The discussion about the use of a resource in the classroom should emphasize, whenever possible, how it can be used to transmit specific content.

In the proposed course, the content was related to the theme of Energy, with the following focuses: Rational Use of Energy and Energy Efficiency, from the perspective of Robotics, and topics covered in the new curriculum of the New High School of the state of São Paulo, within the Curricular Units planned for schools with the Full-Time Education Program (PEI).

The course was conducted in a hybrid format, that is, in a semi-presential format. The in-person activities were held on Saturdays, from 9:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m., at the Center for Innovation in Energy Efficiency – InoVEE, located at UNESP – Guaratinguetá campus. The in-person activities were used to develop conceptual content on robotics, as well as to present a model for developing activities, structured in the form of tasks, and general guidelines for developing teaching projects.

Each in-person meeting was held in a technological workshop format, in which the teachers in the course could carry out the proposed activity individually or in pairs, made up of teachers from the same school. The workshops began by introducing, based on the use of problem situations, the topic to be addressed during the activity. The workshop activities enhanced the use of the stages of computational thinking, namely: decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction and algorithm. Thus, the workshop activities contributed to enriching the training of the teachers taking the course, based on the use of robotics, helping in the development of fundamental skills, such as: logical reasoning, decision-making and creativity.

The project's online activities were developed in 7 (seven) virtual meetings, each lasting 2 (two) hours, aiming to complement the conceptual content presented in the course's in-person activities. In addition to the conceptual content, the training presented topics that were used by the course teachers to develop, together with their students, teaching projects related to the workshop topics.

The online activities were carried out synchronously and asynchronously. In the synchronous mode, the activities were carried out in a "live" format, in which the university team held an online session to answer questions, discussing the solutions to previous exercises provided, and also carrying out reinforcement actions on the content and topics presented in the previous activities. In the asynchronous mode, video classes lasting between 20 and 60 minutes were made available, in addition to complementary materials, such as: handouts, virtual experiments and electronic component manuals. Among the planned online activities, the Virtual Laboratory activities stand out, in which the free simulation software Autodesk Tinkercad™ and Microsoft MakeCode™ software were presented. In both, algorithms were developed for various applications, using programming languages by codes (textual, based on C) or visual (by blocks, based on Scratch™) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Online activity – Virtual Laboratory using Autodesk Tinkercad™ software.

The use of these languages was important for the participants, as they were able to execute the proposed practices, interact with other participants and, in this way, were able to debug, reuse, test and share several educational robotics projects during the online activities. At the end of each online activity, an Evaluation Form was made available, which had to be answered by the participants within a period of up to 7 (seven) days.

5 Results and discussion

We had forty-six (46) teachers enrolled in the course, all of whom were teachers from the public school system in the state of São Paulo, basic education teachers with classes assigned to Elementary or High School in any component, in 2023, and Pedagogical Management Coordinating Teachers (CGP/CGPA/CGPG). Thirty-three (33) teachers completed the course, indicating that 72% of the enrolled teachers were successful at the end of the course. The students were evaluated based on the development of the proposed activities, during the in-person activities, and through evaluation questionnaires, regarding the online actions carried out in the course.

In the in-person activities, carried out in the format of technological workshops, the teachers in the course carried out several projects, among which we can mention: sequential activation of LEDs, construction of a traffic light, color spectrum, generating tones, reverse sensor, electronic tape measure, measuring temperature, night light, electronic data, compass, among others. In this context, the general skills most highlighted by the participants were: scientific, critical and creative thinking; and, among the objects of knowledge, the most cited were: the use of technology and scientific language, the introduction to algorithms and programming logic, and the fundamental notions of electronic circuits. Therefore, the use of technology in the classroom in a consistent/structured way proved to be challenging, but it was also a motivating factor for future applications by the teachers in their classroom activities. And, finally, we highlight that the project-based approach gave the teachers in the course the opportunity to play an active role in the learning process of the content standards worked with the projects.

At the end of the course, an evaluation instrument was administered to the students, containing questions grouped into two groups:

- Group I: objective questions about the course teachers, teaching materials, approaches used, development of planned actions, both in person and online; these questions about expected results and expectations for the development of activities aimed to assess the degree of agreement of the students with the statements presented, according to a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = totally dissatisfied / totally disagree to 5 = very satisfied / totally agree.
- Group II: discursive questions, for students to express their opinions on various aspects of the course.

For group I, 15 statements were listed, for which the degree of agreement of the students was verified. As an example, some of the issues are listed below: (a) The theoretical approach of the course; (b) The practical approach of the course; (c) The teaching materials used; and (d) General organization of the course (facilities, teaching materials, platforms, teachers/instructors, etc.).

Considering, in this analysis, the responses to the options "satisfied" and "very satisfied"/"totally agree", it was observed that the students agreed with all the statements, with satisfaction/agreement percentages above 80%. For example, with regard to statement (a), we obtained a degree of agreement of 88.9%; for statement (b), we obtained a degree of agreement of 96.3%; for statement (c), we obtained a degree of agreement of 92.6%; and, for statement (d), we obtained a 96.3% level of agreement.

As mentioned, group II included essay questions in which students could express themselves on aspects related to the development of the course, such as: the aspects of the course that benefited them the most, the points for improvement in the actions developed, and in both cases, these were separate questions for in-person and online activities. Finally, we requested suggestions for improvements in future editions of the course.

Some of the responses from students regarding the positive aspects of the course, for both in-person and online activities, are listed below:

"Knowledge of the materials in practice, option of block programming, ability to clarify doubts."; "Equipment and components; Availability, cordiality and empathy of the instructors; Facilities."; "Practice, Presence of the Instructors (attentive), solving doubts regarding circuit failure." "Contact with the materials; relationship with other professionals; group work."; "Quality practical classes."; "Teaching materials, dedication of the teachers and teaching methods."; "Well-explained content, practical application together with theory, suitable location."; "The attention of the interns and teachers."; "Resources, dedication of the teachers, practical activities."; "Well-prepared material and attention to the students."; "The teaching methods, easy access and use of the classroom."; "Recorded classes by the teacher, provision of handouts, provision of projects through Tinkercad."; "Attentive teachers, self-explanatory classes and complementary activities."; "Easy-accessible digital material; Files available for download; Q&A."; "Online simulation."; "Supplementary activities, teachers attentive to questions and well-explanatory classes."; "Easy to adapt to schedules, easy-to-learn content, assessment activities to monitor progress."; "Q&A."; "Remote classes allowed me to go back to the questions when I had questions to answer the questionnaires."; "The teaching materials, video classes and virtual laboratory."; "Course length; being able to take the course at home; ease of adjusting the course to my routine." "Q&A, material posted in advance."; "Flexible schedule and recorded classes to revisit the content when necessary."; "Quick and concise classes, didactic and with good image quality, aligned with the theoretical part."

Analyzing the responses of the students, regarding what they liked most, it can be stated that the teaching material developed, as well as the preparation and attention given by the responsible team, professors, UNESP/FEG scholarship holders and collaborators, in the execution of the course's training activities, were positive points that facilitated the monitoring of the course activities. The availability of the programming files of the experiments developed virtually, using the Autodesk Tinkercad™ software and the Microsoft Makecode™ software, was also mentioned as a positive point of the course. The availability of robotics, electronic components and measurement materials, so that the students could develop the planned actions (electronic assemblies of the applications) during the face-to-face workshops, was also indicated as being one of the strong points that most benefited the students during the course. Other points positively evaluated by the students were the implementation of a question-answering service, the quality of the video classes and the other materials made available in the Google Classroom virtual learning environment.

To improve the course, we received suggestions to bring forward the posting and availability of teaching materials for the planned online activities, since prior access to these materials could help students with their participation in the question-and-answer sessions. Another suggestion was to increase the number of weekly question-and-answer sessions, since, with the flexible schedules, students would be able to adjust their schedules to participate in these sessions. Finally, they also suggested creating a WhatsApp group to improve and streamline communication between course instructors and students, with a view to providing more support for the planned online activities.

6 Conclusion

We observed that the course aroused great interest among teachers from public schools in the region of the Guaratinguetá Education Board, considering not only the number of teachers enrolled, but also the discussions regarding the possibility of expanding the target audience of the course at a later date. In this context, the organizing team is considering, as potential future works, the possibility of establishing new partnerships between the University and other Education Boards, or even with local governments in the region, with a view to offering new editions of the course, revised and improved, based on the suggestions and criticisms reported by participants in the course already held.

We can highlight, at the end of this project, that teacher training courses, such as the one described in this article, contribute to a better and more efficient use of new technological resources in the classroom by teachers, meeting the curricular guidelines established for basic education in Brazil. More specifically, in the case of the state of São Paulo, the Educational Robotics course meets the need to better prepare teachers to use robotics kits, made available by the State to several public schools, as well as, more specifically, the need to prepare teachers directly responsible for technology-related subjects in schools.

It is also worth noting that the partnership established between the university (UNESP) and the Education Board of the Guaratinguetá region, aimed at training teachers to use new technologies in the classroom, may be beneficial to UNESP itself, since better-prepared teachers will be able to offer better training to their students. This better training, based on new technologies, may contribute to motivating these students to pursue higher education careers in the exact sciences (for example, by opting for Engineering courses), with the potential for them to become students at the university itself in a few years.

References

- BRASIL. (2018). *Base nacional comum curricular: educação é a base*. Ministério da Educação. http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br/images/BNCC_EI_EF_110518_-versaofinal_site.pdf
- Da Fonseca Silva, S., Ramos Da Silva, J., & Roger Silva, H. (2018, June 26). *Robótica Educacional e a Capacitação de Professores da Educação Infantil* [Paper presentation]. CIET/EnPED - Educação e Tecnologias: Aprendizagem e construção do conhecimento, São Carlos. <https://cietenped.ufscar.br/submissao/index.php/2018/article/view/497>
- Duch, B. J., Groh, S. E., & Allen, D. E. (Eds.). (2006). *El Poder del Aprendizaje Basado en Problemas: Una guía práctica para la enseñanza universitaria*. Fondo Editorial de la Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú.
- Ferraz, A. P. d. C. M., & Belhot, R. V. (2010). Taxonomia de Bloom: revisão teórica e apresentação das adequações do instrumento para definição de objetivos instrucionais. *Gestão & Produção*, 17(2), 421-431. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-530X2010000200015>
- Gerhard, A. C., & Rocha, J. F. B. (2012). A fragmentação dos saberes na educação científica escolar na percepção de professores de uma escola do ensino médio. *Investigações em Ensino de Ciências*, 17(1), 125-145. <https://ienci.if.ufrgs.br/index.php/ienci/article/view/210/144>
- Markham, T., Larmer, J., & Ravitz, J. (2008). *Aprendizagem baseada em projetos: guia para professores de ensino fundamental e médio*. Artmed.
- Martin, F., Mikhak, B., Resnick, M., Silverman, B., and Berg, R. (2000). To Mindstorms and beyond: Evolution of a construction kit for magical machines. In J. Hendler, J. and A. Druin (Eds), *Robots For Kids pp.* 9-33). Morgan Kaufmann.
- Massa, N. P., Oliveira, G. S. d., & Santos, J. A. d. (2022). O Construcionismo de Seymour Papert e os Computadores na Educação. *Cadernos da Fucamp*, 21(52), 110-122.
- Pinto, M. d. C., Elia, M. d. F., & Sampaio, F. F. (2012, November 30). *Formação de professores em Robótica Educacional com hardware livre Arduino no contexto um computador por aluno* [Paper presentation]. Anais do XVIII Workshop de Informática na Escola, Rio de Janeiro - RJ. <https://doi.org/10.5753/wie.2012>
- Pozo, J. I. (Ed.). (1998). *A solução de problemas: aprender a resolver, resolver para aprender*. Artmed.
- Reis, G. L., Souza, L. F. F., Barroso, M. F. S., Pereira, E. B., Nepomuceno, E. G., & Amaral, G. F. (2014). A relevância da integração entre universidades e escolas: um estudo de caso de atividades extensionistas em robótica educacional voltadas para rede pública de ensino. *Interfaces – Rev. de Extensão da UFMG*, 2(3).
- Vargas e Silva, F., Kottwitz, P. W., Rosa, J. A. d., Scheid, R., & Ribeiro, L. d. N. (2018). Uso da robótica como ferramenta para o ensino das ciências exatas. *CATAVENTOS - Revista de Extensão da Universidade de Cruz Alta*, 10(2), 82-93. <https://revistaeletronica.unicruz.edu.br/index.php/cataventos/article/view/101/40>

- Souza, I. M. L., Rodrigues, R. S., & Andrade, W. L. (2016, October 27). [Paper presentation]. Anais dos Workshops do V Congresso Brasileiro de Informática na Educação (CBIE 2016), Uberlândia - MG. <http://milanesa.ime.usp.br/rbie/index.php/wcbie/article/view/7052/4926>
- Tripp, D. (2005). Pesquisa-ação: uma introdução metodológica. *Educação e Pesquisa*, 31(3), 443-466. <https://www.scielo.br/j/ep/a/3DkbXnqBQqyq5bV4TCL9NSH/?format=pdf&lang=pt>